

MONOTERPENOID. PART II. SYNTHESIS OF 2-METHYL-5-*iso*PROPYL-SUBERONE AND 3-METHYL-6-*iso*PROPYLSUBERONE

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Synthesis of 2-methyl-5-*isopropyl*suberone and 3-methyl-6-*isopropyl*suberone, starting from tetrahydrocarvone, has been achieved and their light absorption and other properties have been studied with a view to finding out a method for their estimation in a mixture.

In connection with the projected syntheses in the guaiazulene series, 2-methyl-5-*isopropyl*suberone (I) appeared to be a suitable starting material. It was planned to study the ring-expansion of carvomenthone (II) in this connection. Since the ring-enlargement of tetrahydrocarvone (II) could possibly proceed in either direction to furnish 2-methyl-5-*isopropyl*suberone (I) or 3-methyl-6-*isopropyl*suberone (III), it became necessary to have authentic data about the properties of (I) and (III). This communication describes the synthesis of these hitherto-unknown ketones.

2-Methyl-5-*isopropyl*suberone (I).— The method used for the synthesis of (I) is schematically represented below. The synthesis utilises 1-methyl-4-*isopropyl*-6-oxo-suberic acid (VI) of Bradfield, Jones and Simonsen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 315).

These authors in an effort to prepare the glyoxylate (IV) carried out the condensation of tetrahydrocarvone and diethyl oxalate according to the general method of Kotz and co-workers (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1913, **88**, 261; *Annalen*, 1906, **350**, 217; 1907, **387**, 192). However, the only product isolated proved to be the cleavage material (V). Since this reaction constitutes the starting point for the present synthesis, it has been studied in some details. The authors treated the distilled condensation product with methyl alcoholic potash to hydrolyse the ester, and the acid, thus obtained, was proved to be (VI). In order to find out the stage at which this base-catalysed cleavage must have occurred (*i.e.* during condensation or alkaline hydrolysis), the following reaction was carried out.

The condensation product was heated with glass powder (Bachmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 831) and the distilled material was hydrolysed with acid. Since practically no carvomenthone could be isolated, it was evident that the fission had occurred during condensation. By slightly modifying the conditions for the condensation, somewhat improved yields (77% instead of 64% reported) of the product (V) could be obtained.

The cleavage product (V) was hydrolysed with alkali and the crude acid (VI) obtained was reduced by the Huang-Minlon modification of the Wolf-Kishner reduction to provide 1-methyl-4-isopropylsuberic acid (VII). The reduced acid (VII) was best purified by rectification of its ethyl ester, followed by its hydrolysis. There are not many recorded instances of the reduction of α -keto-acids (Mosbach *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5477). A study of the optimum conditions for this reduction showed that five moles of 60% hydrazine hydrate for each mole of the keto-acid (VI) gave fairly good yields of the required product. Since this method of preparation of (VII) utilises ethyl oxalate to add on a chain of two carbon atoms, it was thought worthwhile to see if the alkaline Wolf-Kishner reduction (*cf.* Stetter *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1954, **87**, 869, 990, 1617) of cyclohexanone-2-glyoxylate could furnish suberic acid itself. This, however, could not be achieved.

For the conversion of 1-methyl-4-isopropylsuberic acid (VII) to 2-methyl-5-isopropylsuberone (I), the dry-distillation method was employed. Of the various modifications (D.R.P., 256,622; Aschan, *Ber.*, 1912, 45, 1603; Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, 9, 249, 399, 499; 1928, 11, 496, 670, 686; Stoll and Rouve, *ibid.*, 1944, 27, 1570; Vogel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2032) of this reaction, the one utilising the various salts (Ruzicka *et al.*, *loc. cit.*; Stoll and Rouve, *loc. cit.*) (especially those of rare earths) has been well investigated. A literature survey showed that the simpler method of Vogel (*loc. cit.*) utilising $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and iron powder afforded superior yields of suberones than the one employing rare-earth salts for dry distillation (cf. Sörm and Fajkos, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1947, 12, 81; Plattner and Studer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 1432; Poinmer, *Annalen*, 1953, 579, 65). Vogel's method, which has been extensively employed by Sörm *et al.* (*Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1947, 12, 251, 554; 1949, 14, 345; 1951, 16, 168, 184; 1955, 20, 227) in the azulene chemistry, was used for the preparation of (I) when consistent yields of 80-85% could be obtained.

The properties of this ketone are recorded in Table I and its spectral properties have been discussed later.

3-Methyl-6-isopropylsuberone (III).—This ketone has been synthesised by following the route outlined below. The keto-ester (XI) and its acid have been described in the literature. The keto-acid has been obtained by the oxidation of carvomenthone with potassium permanganate (Baeyer, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 36), chromic acid (Wallach, *Annalen*, 1905, 339, 113), pervanadic acid (Trieb, *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1199), and by its cleavage with amyl nitrite-HCl (Baeyer, *ibid.*, 1896, 29, 31).

All these procedures furnish the keto-acid in a poor yield. By the application of the base-catalysed ethyl nitrite-ketone fission reaction (Clarke *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 30; Woodward and Doering, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 866; Touster, "Organic Reactions", John Wiley, New York, 1953, Vol. VII, p. 327) to carvomenthone (II), it has been possible to prepare the keto-ester in a yield of 76%. The intermediate oximino-ester (X) was directly converted into (XI) by a short treatment with formalin and hydrochloric acid (Barltrop *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 181; Koelsch and Le Claire, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1941, **6**, 516).

The keto-ester on treatment with ethyl cyanoacetate in the presence of piperidine containing benzylamine (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1953, **30**, 665) readily furnished the desired condensation product (XII), which on catalytic reduction over palladium-on-calcium carbonate (Busch, *Ber.*, 1916, **49**, 1063; 1929, **62**, 1458) yielded the diethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl-5-isopropylsuberate (XIII).

Acid-hydrolysis of (XIII) was slow and incomplete. However, on treatment with potassium hydroxide in ethyleneglycol, both hydrolysis and decarboxylation took place to furnish practically a quantitative yield of the suberic acid (XIV); this was also best purified through its diethyl ester. The dicarboxylic acid (XIV) was converted in a yield of 84% to the corresponding 3-methyl-6-isopropylsuberone (III). The properties of this ketone are recorded in Table I.

The ketones (I) and (III) can both occur as *cis*- and *trans*-stereoisomers, but at present no assignment of configuration is possible.

TABLE I

Properties.	Ketone (I).	Ketone (III)
B.P.	86.87°/2.5 mm	87°/2.5 mm
η_D^{25}	1.4620	1.4610
d_4^{25}	0.9105	0.9075
M_D	50.75 [calc. M_D 50.81]	50.81
$[\alpha]_D^{25}$	+ 6°.81 (<i>c</i> , 2.205% in ethanol)	- 2° 5 (<i>c</i> , 1.583% in ethanol)
$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$	280 μ (ϵ 37)	283 μ (ϵ 26)
$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{n-heptane}}$	285 μ (ϵ 23)	292 μ (ϵ 21)
Odour	Deodar wood	Peppermint

Spectral characteristics.—It is clear from Table I that these two isomeric ketones have very similar physical properties and that a method of estimation cannot be based on them. The ultraviolet light absorption for these compounds has been recorded in Table I. The bathochromic shift for the $\lambda_{\max}$ as well as a decrease in the extinction coefficient ϵ observed for the two suberones in going from a polar to a non-polar solvent is expected (Mariella *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.* 1954, **19**, 678). Since there is not much difference in the $\lambda_{\max}$, estimation by U. V. spectrophotometry on a synthetic mixture in alcohol gave erratic results.

FIG 1

The infra red spectra for the two ketones (I) and (III) are shown in Fig. 1. As expected the C=O stretching vibration occurs at 5.88μ for the ketone (I) and at 5.96μ for the second isomer; it has been established (Rasmussen in Zechmeister's "Progress in the Chemistry of Organic Natural Products", Springer-Verlag, 1948, p. 331) that the C=O frequency is dependent on ring-strain and that suberones* absorb more at lower frequency than the 6-membered ketones. The bands at 7.11μ and 7.15μ for the ketones (I) and (III) respectively are to be ascribed to the scissoring frequency of the methylene group next to the carbonyl (Jones and Sandorfy in Weissberger's "Technique of Organic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1956, Vol. IX, p. 498). Whereas the ketone (II) shows a well-defined doublet at 7.3μ , characteristic of the gem-dimethyl (Bellamy, "The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 23), it is not so well defined in the isomer (I). In the fingerprint region, (I) exhibits two characteristic bands at 10.92μ and 11.2μ , which are not present in (II), and consequently can be utilised for its estimation; similarly ketone (II) has a band at 11.56μ useful for its determination.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra were measured on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer.

Tetrahydrocarvone (II).—The carvone used in these experiments had b. p. $150.52^\circ/50$ mm, $126.27^\circ/34$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4970, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ + $57^\circ.2$.

A mixture of freshly distilled carvone (37.5 g., 0.25 M), ethanol (distilled over Raney nickel) and Pd-CaCO₃ catalyst (6 g.) was hydrogenated in the usual manner. The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated through an efficient column. The desired product was collected at $115.16^\circ/30$ mm; the η_D^{25} varied as the distillation proceeded from 1.4535 to 1.4538 and the $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ changed from $-31^\circ.4$ to -26° ; yield 64-66%. A higher boiling fraction with b. p. $117.34^\circ/30$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4925 and $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -12° amounted to about 30% (Read and Johnston, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 226, record for tetrahydrocarvone; b. p. $98.99^\circ/16$ mm, η_D^{25} 1.4552, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ $-30^\circ 37'$).

1-Methyl-4-isopropyl-6-oxosuberic Acid (VI).—To an ice-cooled solution of sodium (16.1 g., 0.7 g. atom) in absolute ethanol (200 c.c.) a well-cooled mixture of carvomenthone (90 g., 0.584M) and ethyl oxalate (108 g., 0.74M) was added during a few minutes with swirling. The light orange mixture was allowed to stand at $0^\circ-5^\circ$ for 36 hours and then at room temperature (25°) for another 12 hours. The reddish solution was then poured on ice (500 g.) and H₂SO₄ (C.P., 30 c.c.) covered with ether (150 c.c.). The solvent layer was separated and the aqueous phase extracted with ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 2). The combined extracts were washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate (50 c.c. $\times$ 2) and then with brine (50 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was distilled off (column) and the residue fractionated. The required product (V) distilled at b. p. $152.55^\circ/1.5$ mm; η_D^{25} 1.4610-1.4595, yield 75-77% (131-135 g.).

* Suberone has been stated to exhibit its C=O band at 1699 cm^{-1} (Scott and Tarbell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 240).

(1703 (liquid) (Sörm, et al., *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1950, 18, 186),
1694 (solution).

The above product (81.1 g.) was refluxed with methanolic KOH (60 g. of KOH in 50 c.c. water and 600 c.c. MeOH) for 3 hours. This was filtered to remove a small precipitate and then most of the alcohol was distilled off. The residue was diluted with water (100 c.c.) and extracted with ether to remove any neutral material. The alkaline portion was acidified with HCl (dil.), saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether (75 c.c. $\times$ 4). The combined extract was washed once with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent left the crude acid (VI) as a gum; yield 63.3 g. (96%). This was used as such in the next step.

In order to determine the stage at which cleavage had occurred, the keto-ester (V; 5.8 g.) was heated with glass powder (3 g.) at 160-70° for 2 hours and worked up with ether. The product was distilled in vacuum: b.p. 164°/13 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4495, yield 4.15 g. This material was refluxed with HCl (C.P., 25 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.) for 10 hours and treated with sodium bicarbonate to separate acidic and neutral portions; the latter was negligible.

1-Methyl-4-isopropylsuberic Acid (VII).—To a solution of KOH (60 g.) in ethyleneglycol (300 c.c.) the above keto-acid (36.5 g., 0.15 M) and hydrazine hydrate (60%, 62.5 c.c., 0.75 M) were added. After refluxing for 3½ hours, the excess of hydrazine hydrate and water were allowed to escape during 2 hours till the contents registered a temperature of 190-95°. The product was again refluxed for another 6 hours, cooled, diluted with water (100 c.c.), acidified with HCl and extracted with ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 4) after salting with brine. From the combined extracts, solvent was flashed off and the residue was diluted with benzene (40 c.c.), which was distilled off. The crude acid (VII), thus obtained, was esterified by heating it with benzene (40 c.c.), alcohol (25 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 0.5 c.c.) through azeotropic distillation. The separation of water ceased after one hour, but the heating was continued for another hour. The product was cooled and washed with water (20 c.c. $\times$ 2). The aqueous portion was extracted with benzene (20 c.c.) and the combined benzene solutions washed once with brine containing sodium carbonate, and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was removed (column) and the crude ester fractionated to afford the *diethyl 1-methyl-4-isopropylsuberate* as a colorless liquid: b.p. 141°/2 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4410, yield 31 g. (73%). An analytical sample had b.p. 135°/1.5 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4390, d_4^{20} 0.9504, M_b 79.12 (calc. 79.42), M.W. by saponification, 290.4 (calc. 286). (Found: C, 67.22; H, 10.76. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.13; H, 10.49%).

The pure ester (85.5 g., 0.3 M) was saponified with ethanolic KOH (50 g. KOH, 50 c.c. water, 450 c.c. of alcohol) by gently refluxing for 12 hours. The alcohol was distilled off, the residue cooled, diluted with water (200 c.c.), washed once with ether and acidified with HCl (Congo red). After saturation with sodium chloride, the acid was taken up in ether (150 c.c. $\times$ 3) washed with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent left the acid (68.4 g., 99.5%) as a thick liquid, which failed to solidify. An analytical sample was prepared by short-path distillation from a 'rocket' (bath temperature 130°/0.05 mm). (Found: C, 62.69; H, 9.74. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.62; H, 9.56%).

2-Methyl-5-isopropylcycloheptanone (I).—Iron powder (Merck) was heated in a current of pure, dry hydrogen at 450° for 4 hours and then allowed to cool in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The preparation was used up within a month.

The dibasic acid (VII: 16.3 g.) was thoroughly mixed with the above iron powder (16.3 g.) and finely powdered crystalline barium hydroxide (1 g.) in a distillation flask (125 c.c.). The neck of the flask was fitted with a thermometer dipping into the mixture and the whole was assembled for distillation. The mixture was heated manually with a free flame. A lot of fumes evolved in the beginning, followed by a few drops of water. The ketone started distilling at 280°, but the contents were heated strongly so that the inside temperature was 300°-360°. After the pyrolysis was over ($\frac{3}{4}$ hour), the flask was cooled and then water (30 c.c.) was added which was distilled off to co-distil any residual ketone. The product was taken up in ether (20 c.c. $\times$ 3), washed with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was carefully removed (column) and the residue distilled to give a colorless liquid with an intense odour of "deodar" wood, b.p. 74°/1 mm, yield 10 g. (84%). The properties of the analytical sample have been recorded in Table I. (Found: C, 78.51; H, 11.91. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 78.57; H, 11.91%).

The *semicarbazone* (pyridine method) after three crystallisations from dilute alcohol was obtained as white lustrous leaflets, m.p. 150-51°. (Found: N, 18.58. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{23}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 18.66%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* (H_2SO_4 method) after three crystallisations from alcohol furnished lustrous yellow plates, m.p. 115.5-16°. (Found: N, 16.54. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 16.09%).

Ethyl 2-isoPropyl-5-oxo-n-heptanoate (XI).—Ethyl nitrite was dried over solid KOH and was distilled from it immediately before use.

To well-cooled carvomenthone (32.8 g., 0.213M), contained in a litre flask protected from moisture, an ice-cold solution of sodium (4.9 g., 0.213 g. atom) in alcohol (100 c.c.) was added. This was diluted with absolute alcohol (500 c.c.) and then thoroughly chilled. Ethyl nitrite (27 g., 0.36 M) was added in one lot with swirling and cooling. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at 0°-5° for 18 hours. Through the reddish orange solution, thus obtained, dry carbon dioxide was bubbled for about 3 hours, warmed and the precipitated sodium carbonate filtered off. The alcohol was removed (column) from a steam-bath to afford the crude oximino ester. To this formaldehyde (40%; 25 c.c.) and HCl (2N, 7.8 c.c.) were added and the mixture warmed on a steam-bath for 10 minutes with swirling, when the top layer became dark. This was cooled and the product extracted with ether (25 c.c. $\times$ 5) and the combined extracts washed with sodium carbonate solution (20 c.c. $\times$ 2) and then with brine (20 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The material was stripped off the solvent and the residue fractionated to give after a small fore-run (1.75 g.) the desired keto-ester (XI) as a colorless liquid: b.p. 123-26°/6mm, n_D^{27} 1.4385, yield 30.7 g. (75.8%). (Baeyer, (*loc. cit.*) records b.p. 143-46°/12 mm.

An analytical sample (refractionated: central cut) had b. p. 116-18°/3.5 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4380, d_4^{25} 0.9543, M_D 58.84 (calc. 59.3), $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -1° 2.

Diethyl 1-Cyano-2-methyl-5-isopropyl- Δ^1 -suberate (XII).—A mixture of the keto-ester (XI: 36.95 g., 0.173 M), ethyl cyanoacetate (22.6 g., 0.2 M), piperidine (1.53 g., 0.018 M), benzylamine (0.214 g.), glacial acetic acid (6 c.c.) and benzene (100 c.c.) was refluxed with the continuous removal of water. Separation of water ceased after one hour. After heating for another $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour, the product was cooled, diluted with ether (200 c.c.) and washed successively with water (30 c.c. $\times$ 2) and brine (50 c.c. $\times$ 1). After drying (Na_2SO_4) the solvent was removed and the residue fractionated (Vigreux column). The condensation product was obtained as a colorless liquid: b.p. 170-75°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4695, yield 47.3 g. (88.6%).

A sample was refractionated for analysis: b.p. 149-73°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4700, d_4^{25} 1.016, M_D 84.89 (calc. 83.3, EM_D 1.59, $E_{\Sigma D}$ 0.51), $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -10°.2. (Found: C, 66.15; H, 8.76; N, 4.6. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 66.01; H, 8.74; N, 4.53%).

Diethyl 1-Cyano-2-methyl-5-isopropylsuberate (XIII).—The above unsaturated ester (49.9 g., 0.161 M) in ethanol (distilled over Raney nickel, 200 c.c.) was hydrogenated over Pd- CaCO_3 catalyst (5 g) at room temperature and pressure. The reduction came to a close after a take-up of 101% of the theoretical amount of hydrogen during 16-20 hours. After processing in the usual way the product was fractionated to yield a colorless liquid: b.p. 169°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4480, yield 47.4 g. (94.4%).

A purified sample had b.p. 169°/2 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4480, d_4^{25} 0.9974, M_D 83.51 (calc. 83.79), $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -3°.2. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 9.29; N, 4.29. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{29}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 65.53; H, 9.32; N, 4.5%).

Diethyl 2-Methyl-5-isopropylsuberate.—The reduced cyano-ester (XIII; 13.9 g.) was refluxed with KOH (10 g. in 10 c.c. of water) in ethyleneglycol (60 c.c.) till the evolution of ammonia had ceased (7-10 hours). The cooled material was diluted with water (50 c.c.) and washed once with ether to remove the neutral products. The alkaline solution was acidified with HCl to p_H 2, saturated with sodium chloride and extracted with ether (25 c.c. $\times$ 4). The combined extract was washed with brine and dried. The solvent was removed and the crude acid was mixed with benzene (30 c.c.) which was distilled off to remove any moisture. The residue was refluxed with benzene (80 c.c.), alcohol (40 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (C.P., 8 c.c.) for 17 hours. This was cooled, diluted with water (100 c.c.), the solvent phase separated and the aqueous portion extracted with benzene (20 c.c. $\times$ 3). The benzene extracts were worked up as usual (*vide supra*) to give the required ester as a colorless liquid: b.p. 138-39°/1.5 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4390, yield 12.2 g. (95%).

A sample refractionated for analysis had b.p. 138-39°/1.5 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4380, d_4^{25} 0.9495, M_D 79.0 (calc. 79.3), M.W. by saponification 288.2 (calc. 286). (Found: C, 65.99; H, 10.36. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.13; H, 10.49%).

2-Methyl-5-isopropylsuberic Acid (XIV).—The above ester (5.27 g.) was refluxed with ethanolic KOH (KOH 6 g., water 15 c.c. and ethanol 85 c.c.) for 6 hours and worked up as described for (VII). The acid was obtained as a thick liquid, yield 4.05 g. (95.6%). A sample was purified for analysis by evaporative distillation (bath temperature 160°/0.07 mm). (Found: C, 62.12; H, 9.74. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 62.62; H, 9.56%).

3-Methyl-6-isopropylsuberone (III) was prepared from the above acid (XIV: 5.7 g.), iron powder (6.1 g.) and barium hydroxide (0.25 g.) in a manner described for the isomeric ketone (I). The decomposition temperature was almost the same and the ketone was obtained as a colorless liquid with a strong peppermint odour: b.p. $125^{\circ}/40$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.4620, yield 3.5 g. (84.1%). The properties of the analytical sample have been recorded in Table I. (Found: C, 78.49; H, 11.91. $C_{11}H_{20}O$ requires C, 78.57; H, 11.91%).

The semicarbazone (pyridine method) after four crystallisations from alcohol was obtained in white small needles, m.p. 154° . (Found: N, 19.0. $C_{13}H_{23}ON_3$ requires N, 18.66%).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (H_2SO_4 method) (crude: m.p. about 75°) crystallised from alcohol in deep orange plates, m.p. $97-98^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 16.48. $C_{17}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires N, 16.1%).

Infra-red Spectra.—These were taken by the courtesy of Sadtler Research Laboratories (Philadelphia, U.S.A.) on pure liquids (cell width 0.01 mm, NaCl prism) on Baird Associates I.R. spectrophotometer.

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